

**FEATURES OF TEACHING AUTOCAD AT A
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ABSTRACT

This article outlines the purpose of gaining knowledge in the fundamentals of engineering graphics. It explores object modification, which enables the creation of new geometric configurations from the original drawing objects, and the creation of new coordinate systems, while defining the spatial position relative to the previous system using the UCS command. It also presents methods for standardizing drawing documentation, organizing work with a file of electronic drawing sheets grouped according to a common thematic feature, and developing skills in processing and printing simple drawings to obtain a paper copy of the electronic drawing..

Studying engineering graphics at a university is a special course in training specialists in the Information Systems field. Engineers, designers, construction workers, and others at enterprises now have the opportunity to create their own drawings, diagrams, and sketches using an automated graphics package.

AutoCAD is a widely used program, having evolved from the primary computer-aided drafting program for personal computers into one of the most advanced and powerful design tools available today. This product is quite versatile and offers extensive additional features. The multitude of menus, toolbars, and dialog boxes filled with commands, parameters, and system variable settings can be overwhelming for students. Therefore, learning AutoCAD requires a well-planned strategy. If you are new to computer-aided drafting, and AutoCAD in particular, the first step to mastering it is familiarizing yourself with the screen layout. If you are unfamiliar with computers, it is advisable to gain some knowledge of working with files.

In order for students to successfully develop a drawing, they must first be taught design documentation, where the dimensions of objects must be maintained precisely.

In this course, students study the general concepts of computer-aided design systems, since the name of the system itself is derived from the abbreviated English phrase Automated Computer Aided Drafting and Design, which means "automated drawing and design using a computer," the features of launching the program, calling commands, methods for setting up and creating toolbars, study the setting of drawing parameters in AutoCAD, the concept of the basics of creating a drawing, drawing various objects, mastering the methods of entering coordinates and the general methodology of using engineering graphics in professional work.

The primary objectives of this course are to: develop students' understanding of the fundamentals of engineering graphics; study object modification, which enables the creation of new geometric configurations from the original drawing objects; create a new coordinate system, while defining its spatial position relative to the previous system using the UCS command; present methods for standardizing drawing documentation; organize work with a file of electronic drawing sheets, united by a single thematic feature; and develop skills in processing and outputting simple drawings to a printing device to obtain a paper copy of the electronic drawing.

The difficulty in studying this course is that, unlike graphic editors (such as PhotoShop or Paintbrush), AutoCAD works not with images per se, but with geometric descriptions of objects, which is dictated by the tasks of CAD. For example, in the internal representation of the AutoCAD graphic editor, a line segment is described by two points, a circle is described by a center and a radius, and so on. On the one hand, a drawing with a geometric description of objects allows for various high-precision geometric constructions and transformations (which are constantly required in engineering practice), as well as the direct use of the geometric model in studying its strength properties and in preparing for the production of the designed product. Design and drafting are areas of strict information, requiring the use of precise graphic and descriptive guidelines. Drawing rules and specific disciplines (architecture, mechanics, electricity, technological process, surveying, structures/construction, etc.) have migrated from traditional whiteboard drafting to automated drafting.

A comparison can be made between the drawing area on the AutoCAD screen and the drawing sheet on a draftsman's whiteboard. For example, both the drawing area of AutoCAD and the sheet on a draftsman's whiteboard represent planes. Sometimes the approach taken to creating objects on the computer is similar to that taken by a draftsman using a whiteboard. However, at times, these approaches differ significantly. Whiteboard draftsmen use lines, circles, arcs, and freehand elements on the flat surface of the drawing sheet to relate projections of real, solid, three-dimensional objects onto the whiteboard surface. For example, a circle might be drawn to represent a sphere or the edge of a cylinder, a triangle to represent a cone or pyramid, and a rectangle might represent the side projection of a piece of pipe or the edge of a 2x4 wooden dowel, as shown in Figure 1:

Fig. 1. How different objects are represented in two-dimensional drawing: sphere, cylinder, cone, pyramid, long narrow cylinder, long thin block

When a draftsman using a drawing board draws an object on paper, the object's points are typically located at a specific distance and in a specific direction from a reference point. This reference point may belong to the object itself or to another object on the drawing. For example, when drawing a parcel of land, the corners of the parcel are typically specified by their relationship to other corners. A surveyor drawing the parcel will specify the points using

the "intersection and boundary" method, i.e., by specifying the direction and distance of one point from another.

The basic drawing elements created on a computer are similar to those created by draftsmen on a blackboard.

In AutoCAD, the drawing area displayed on the screen represents a specific area on a plane in a simulated computer space. This plane is a typical two-dimensional drawing surface in AutoCAD. If you imagine your viewpoint as an "eye in the sky" and want to draw a fence, a tree, and a building, you could draw a line, a circle, and a rectangle on the surface to represent these three objects. For anyone studying your drawing, this is a fundamental method for relating the relative sizes and positions of solid objects. Like an artist preparing to paint a picture, you use the surface on the AutoCAD drawing screen as a canvas.

AutoCAD implements these rules with many additional capabilities. However, AutoCAD does not automatically select the correct symbol, dimension, linetype, or other drawing aspect to apply to the current drawing. Students must know what the final product is expected to look like.

For example, one discipline may require arrows at the ends of dimension lines, while another requires crosses in their place. AutoCAD makes it easy to draw any type of symbol. But as a draftsman and designer using CAD, you must be knowledgeable enough to know which symbol to use. Computer power and speed are no substitute for your professional knowledge and won't help you determine what the final drawing should look like.

Thus, a unique feature of AutoCAD training is that in recent years, the program has gained extraordinary popularity worldwide, including in our country, and is used in many industries and construction thanks to its truly inexhaustible capabilities. The AutoCAD package is designed for any specialist working with technical or presentation graphics. The system's developers, with a wide range of users in mind, incorporated extensive adaptability into the package for any subject area. This adaptation has opened up the possibility of using AutoCAD by specialists in various fields. At the same time, the need has arisen for both specialists with technical training and ordinary users to learn the basics of AutoCAD

References:

- 1 Mark Smith, Bud Middleburk , for dummies, trans. from English..language. / Mark Smith, Bud Middlebury . - M.: 2001.
- 2 Poleshchuk, N. Self-study Guide to AutoCAD 2002 / N. Poleshchuk . - St. Petersburg: BHV, 2000.
- 3 Pogorelov, V. I. AutoCAD 2006. Modeling in space for engineers and designers / V. I. Pogorelov. - St. Petersburg : BHV , 2006.
- 4 Sokolova, T. Yu. AutoCAD 100% / T. Yu. Sokolova. - St. Petersburg: Piter, 2006.
- 5 Yarwood , A. 2000: Lessons for Beginners. Translated from English / A. Yarwood - M.: Mir, 2000. - 435 p.